

Synthesis and hydrolytic stability of new lactoferricin analogues

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Abstract

The effectiveness and therapeutic potency of most biologically active organic compounds (drugs), including peptides, are determined to some extent by their hydrolytic stability. The selection of a pharmacologically active structural motif is essential in the development of new therapeutics. It determines, to a large extent, both the hydrolytic stability of the new molecule and its pharmacokinetic (including dynamic) behavior in the body. The aim of this study is to evaluate the hydrolytic stability of the synthesized LfcinB analogues under physiological conditions such as body temperature (37 °C) and physiological values of pH = 2.0 (gastric juice), pH = 7.4 (blood plasma), and pH = 9.0 (duodenum and small intestine).

Keywords

Antimicrobial peptides, hydrolytic stability, lactoferricin, SPPS

Introduction

According to the World Health Organization (WHO), there is an alarming increase in bacterial infections caused by resistant microorganisms, which is a global public health problem. A large part of the most severe socially significant modern diseases (neoplasia, neurodegenerative diseases, among others) are associated with microbial infections. Critical problems include the pharmaco-economic aspect in the treatment of individual patients, increased morbidity of the population, prolonged hospitalization, high treatment costs, and others. In the therapy of infectious diseases, the possibility of using antimicrobial drugs is becoming increasingly narrow. In Europe, during 2020, a positive trend was observed in reducing the to-

tal consumption of antibiotics by an average of 18%. This is mainly due to increased hygiene and social distancing measures related to COVID-19. Bulgaria is the only country in which there was an increase of about 30% in the use of antibiotics in 2020 in the outpatient sector (Hashiguchi et al. 2022). Overconsumption is observed with antibiotics from the groups of macrolides and fluoroquinolones. Bulgaria reports a growth of over 100% in the use of azithromycin in outpatient care (Mihaylova et al. 2022).

Over the past few decades, scientists have focused their efforts on designing, developing, and obtaining therapeutic agents that do not induce resistance and can be used to treat infections caused by resistant pathogens. One such example is the research on lactoferricin (Lfcin). These are cationic antibacterial peptides included in the iron chelate complex

of the protein lactoferrin and are located in the N-terminal region of the molecule (Huertas Méndez et al. 2017). In the mammalian body, Lfcin is formed naturally after hydrolysis of LF by pepsin (Tomita et al. 1991). It is found in mucous secretions (eyes, breast, respiratory tract, oropharynx, vagina, seminal fluid, and breast milk), both in humans (LfcinH) and in cattle (LfcinB), goats (LfcinC), and mice (LfcinM).

LfcinB interacts with the bacterial membrane through electrostatic forces of attraction between negatively charged molecules on the bacterial surface and positively charged amino acid residues within the molecule. Hydrophobic residues in the peptide chain (such as tryptophan (Trp)) interact with the lipid bilayer, disrupt membrane stability, increase permeability, and lead to its rupture (Aguilera et al. 1999; Ulvatne et al. 2001; Moretta et al. 2021). Bovine Lfcin is a 25-amino-acid cationic peptide that contains a large number of basic amino acids, has a positive net charge (+8), and has amphipathic properties (Bellamy et al. 1992). LfcinB exhibits more potent antimicrobial activity than LfcinH due to the presence of the 20–25 fragment in its structure. This fragment is amphipathic and is the minimum sequence of six amino acids (RRWQWR) exhibiting antimicrobial activity due to the high content of Arg- and Trp-residues (Huertas Méndez et al. 2017).

In this context, our first aim was to synthesize short model peptide fragments of LfcinB containing the basic amino acids Arg and Lys, as well as the D-amino acid D-Tyr(Et).

The second aim of this study was to evaluate the hydrolytic stability of newly synthesized LfcinB analogues under physiological conditions such as body temperature (37 °C) and values of pH = 2.0 (gastric juice), pH = 7.4 (blood plasma), and pH = 9.0 (duodenum and small intestine).

Material and methods

Na-Fmoc-protected AAs: Fmoc-L-Phe-OH; Fmoc-L-Arg(Pbf)-OH; Fmoc-L-Lys(Boc)-OH; Fmoc-D-Tyr(Et)-OH; Fmoc-L-Gln-OH; Fmoc-L-Trp(Boc)-OH were purchased from Iris Biotech GmbH (Germany) and Merck (Germany).

Reagents for peptide synthesis: protection reagents: Fmoc-OSu (Iris Biotech GmbH, Germany); (Boc)₂O (Fluka); condensing reagents: TBTU, HBTU, HOBt, BOP, PyBop (Iris Biotech GmbH, Germany); bases: DIPEA (Fluka), Et₃N (Ferak), NaHCO₃, piperidine (Merck); organic solvents: DCM; MeOH; EtOH; EtOAc; 2-PrOH; (C₂H₅)₂O; DMF (Merck); reagents used to unblock AA: 20% piperidine (Merck); 20% piperidine/DMF; TFA (Merck); 1% TFA/DCM; resins (Iris Biotech GmbH, Germany): 2-chlorotrityl chloride resin (Iris Biotech GmbH, Germany); HL-Arg(Pbf)-chlorotrityl chloride resin (Merck and Iris Biotech GmbH, Germany).

Peptide synthesis

Peptide synthesis was carried out by the solid-phase peptide synthesis (SPPS) method, using the Fmoc/*t*Bu strategy for the construction of the peptide chain. The latter

involves the use of 2-chlorotrityl chloride resin (2,α-dichlorobenzhydryl-polystyrene) cross-linked with 1% divinylbenzene (DVB) at a loading of 1.4 mmol/g. Sequential coupling of each amino acid was performed in the presence of a 2 mol excess of Fmoc-AA, 1 mol HOBT (1H-benzotriazole-1-ol), 1 mol PyBOP (benzotriazol-1-yl-oxytrypyrrolidinophosphonium hexafluorophosphate), and a 2 mol excess of N,N-diisopropylethylamine (DIPEA) in dimethylformamide (DMF). Completion of each stage of AA accession was monitored using the Kaiser test. The Fmoc group was cleaved by adding 20% piperidine to DMF. Cleavage of the peptide from the resin and simultaneous deblocking of the side chains (removal of the Boc and *t*Bu-protecting groups) were done by washing by threefold addition of an aqueous solution of trifluoroacetic acid (TFA) and triisopropyl silane (TIPS). The reaction was carried out at room temperature, and the extracted amount of peptide was precipitated with diethyl ether and filtered cold at about 5 °C. The resulting peptides were dissolved in a minimal amount of distilled water and purified by gel filtration on Sephadex G-25 with CH₃COOH as eluent. The filtrates were collected and lyophilized for about 12 hours to a dry mass. The chemical purity of the peptides was characterized by RP-HPLC and capillary electrophoresis. The structural identity of the peptides was determined by measuring the molecular mass of the compounds using electrospray ionization mass spectrometry (ESI-MS).

Hydrolytic stability

The analysis of the short-term chemical and hydrolytic stability of the peptide analogues was carried out using the method of UV-Vis spectroscopy. All experiments were carried out with a UV-Vis spectrophotometer, model T60 (PG Instruments Limited, UK). The spectra of the studied peptides were taken in a quartz cuvette (with a capacity of 4.0 mL) with an optical path thickness of 1.0 cm, in the interval 240–280 nm.

All samples were tested in solution (concentration 0.5×10^{-4} mol/L). To determine their hydrolytic stability, we investigated their behavior in three different buffer media with pH close to that of physiological conditions, namely, gastric juice (pH = 2.0), blood plasma (pH = 7.4), and duodenum and small intestine (pH = 9.0). The working solutions were thermostated at 37 °C.

Aliquots of 3.0 mL of each working solution were pipetted at equal time intervals (0, 60, 120, 180, 240, 300, and 360 min) to monitor hydrolytic stability.

Results and discussion

For the modeling of short peptide analogues of LfcinB, the numerous structure–effect relationship studies reported to date have been taken into account. They show that the most active and selectively acting analogues are those that have both the basic amino acids Arg and Lys in

their molecule (Dean et al. 2011; Cárdenas-Martínez et al. 2021), as well as the aromatic Trp. To improve the stability of peptides, a very suitable approach is modification by adding D-amino acids, unnatural amino acids, and analogues of aromatic AK (Tyr).

It has also been shown that changes at any single position of the peptide can affect other residues at all other positions in the parent molecule. According to Hilpert et al., each individual modified peptide variant may result in different activity and stability (Hilpert et al. 2006).

In this context, our first goal was to synthesize cationic peptides with high yield and purity. All modifications were made at the N-terminus of the hexapeptide molecules (Fig. 1).

Using the solid-phase method, we obtained hexapeptides LfcinB1, LfcinB3, and LfcinB6. The first synthesized peptide (LfcinB1) possesses the same amino acid sequence as that of the natural oligopeptide, while the other two analogues are modified by substitutions made at the second (LfcinB3) and the third (LfcinB6) positions in the peptide structure.

After purification by Sephadex G-25 gel filtration, the peptides were isolated in high yield and excellent purity (>95%), confirmed by RP-HPLC (Fig. 2) and capillary electrophoresis.

Hydrolysis is the main metabolic transformation determining the plasma half-life of a biological peptide. The rate at which the amide bond is hydrolyzed depends on the temperature and pH of the medium. Once in the stomach contents, the peptides are denatured. Subsequently, under the action of peptidases, they lose their

structural integrity. Knowledge of the behavior of a given compound in buffer solutions of different pH would allow determination of the limits at which it retains its structure and concentration over time. This, in turn, significantly helps determine the conditions under which the molecule is most susceptible to degradation, which is taken into account in subsequent optimization processes.

Therefore, to determine the hydrolytic stability of the synthesized lactoferricin B analogues, we investigated their behavior at three different physiological values of pH = 2 (stomach), pH = 7.4 (blood plasma), and pH = 9.0 (duodenum and small intestine) using UV spectroscopy and RP-HPLC. At certain intervals of time, we measured the absorbance in the interval 240–280 nm. Time/concentration plots were plotted for each of the investigated peptides. Fig. 3 shows the hydrolytic stability of Arg-Arg-Trp-Gln-Trp-Arg (LfcinB1).

Throughout the study (up to the 6th hour), the LfcinB1 oligopeptide showed relative structural stability in acidic and alkaline buffer pH environments. In a neutral environment, however, the same peptide exhibits some structural instability (Fig. 3).

Similar to LfcinB1, the newly synthesized analogue Arg-Lys-Trp-Gln-Trp-Arg (LfcinB3) demonstrated high structural stability in acidic and alkaline solution pH environments. In a neutral pH environment, it is more stable than LfcinB1 and retains its stability until the fourth hour (Fig. 4), after which some structural changes in the absorbability of the hexapeptide are observed. We associate the changes with the chemical (hydrolytic) changes in the composition of the analyzed analyte.

Figure 1. Substitutions made in the structure of the newly synthesized oligopeptides.

Figure 2. RP-HPLC chromatographic profile of the LfcinB analogue.

Figure 3. UV spectra of LfcinB1 in buffer media of pH 2, pH 7, and pH 9.

Figure 4. UV spectra of LfcinB3 in buffer media of pH 2, pH 7, and pH 9.

Figure 5. UV spectra of LfcinB6 in buffer media of pH 2, pH 7, and pH 9.

The structural stability of Arg-Arg-D-Tyr(Et)-Gln-Trp-Arg (LfcinB6) in all three environments (Fig. 5) was relatively high and preserved within the experiment.

The chemical stability of peptides is highly dependent on the amino acid composition and sequence.

Conclusion

From the obtained experimental results, it can be concluded that:

- In an acidic pH environment, all three hexapeptides (LfcinB1, LfcinB3, and LfcinB6) exhibit relatively high structural stability;
- In a neutral pH medium, the LfcinB6 oligopeptide exhibits structural integrity. The peptide analogue LfcinB3 was stable up to the fourth hour, and throughout the study period the stability of LfcinB1 decreased progressively;
- In an alkaline medium, peptides LfcinB1, LfcinB3, and LfcinB6 retain their structural integrity throughout the experimental course.

In summary, peptide LfcinB1 and the analogues LfcinB3 and LfcinB6 exhibit maximum structural stability in environments with different pH.

Additional information

Conflict of interest

The authors have declared that no competing interests exist.

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Ethical statements

The authors declared that no clinical trials were used in the present study.

The authors declared that no experiments on humans or human tissues were performed for the present study.

The authors declared that no informed consent was obtained from the humans, donors or donors' representatives participating in the study.

The authors declared that no experiments on animals were performed for the present study.

The authors declared that no commercially available immortalised human and animal cell lines were used in the present study.

Use of AI

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Data availability

All of the data that support the findings of this study are available in the main text.

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